

A Study on the Histopathological Changes in the Placenta of Pre-Eclampsia MothersM. Vasantha Malini¹, G.V. Sivaprasad², Surekha Teki³¹Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology NRI Institute of Medical Sciences, Sangivalasa, Visakhapatnam²Professor and HOD, Department of Anatomy, NRI Institute of Medical Sciences, Sangivalasa, Visakhapatnam³Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was done to see the histopathological changes in the placenta of Pre-Eclampsia (PE) mothers when compared to that of the normotensive mothers.**Methods:** A comparative study was done on 100 fresh placenta were collected from the labour room of NRI institute of medical sciences [50 normal (controls), 50 Pre-Eclampsia (cases)] and they were observed for any gross structural changes like presence of calcifications, retro-placental haematomas. Sections were taken from the placenta and histopathological study was done to see the presence of syncytial knots, fibrinoid necrosis, stromal fibrosis and calcifications in HE staining under compound microscope. The results were analysed using SPSS 17 software.**Results:** In the present study pre-eclampsia was found to be more common in females of the age group 21-25 yrs (36 out of 50 cases i.e, 72%). Out of the 50 placenta collected from pre-eclampsia cases 20(40%) have shown infarction, 26(52%) have shown calcifications, 11(22%) have shown retroplacental clots macroscopically and 27 (54%) cases have shown syncytial knots, 22 (44%) cases have shown fibrinoid necrosis, 26(52%) have shown stromal fibrosis 18(36%) have shown calcifications and, 14(28%) have shown infarcts as microscopic features. The mean foetal birth weight (1946.32) and mean placental weight (420.04) is significantly low in the cases when compared to the mean foetal birth weight (2854.04) and placental weight (504.00) in the controls with a p-value less than 0.001 making the study statistically significant. The Apgar score after 5 min was reduced in the babies of pre-eclampsia cases (p value < 0.001) suggesting hypoxia and 3 out of 50 babies were admitted in NICU for further management.**Conclusion:** Based on the histopathological changes noted in the study it can be concluded that preeclampsia has adverse effect on morphology of placenta and consequently affects the foetal outcome. Hence the knowledge about the histopathological changes would be important to the gynaecologists in treating the subsequent pregnancies. Every effort should be made to prevent PE and severe forms of PE by giving prophylactic medications like low dose aspirin and calcium supplements in their subsequent pregnancies and women at high risk of developing PE.**Keywords:** Syncytial Knots, Fibrinoid Necrosis, Calcifications.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The human placenta is a dynamic and complex interface between the maternal and embryonic tissues. The placenta is a fetomaternal organ possessing various complex functions. It establishes an interface for the exchange of gases and nutrients between the fetal and maternal circulation [1]. Hypertensive disorders complicating pregnancy are common in about 8-10% of pregnancies. It forms one of the deadly triad, along with haemorrhage & infection, which contribute greatly to maternal & foetal morbidity & mortality. [2] In Pre-Eclampsia, pathological changes noted in the placenta are infarction, calcifications, diffuse

placental thrombosis, and abnormal trophoblastic proliferation. It results in reduced blood flow across placenta and uteroplacental insufficiency. [3] Naeye and Friedman (1979) calculated that 70% of excess foetal deaths in women with hypertension are due to placental infarcts. It has been shown that the maternal utero-placental blood flow is very much decreased in Pre-Eclampsia due to maternal vasospasm. It causes indirect constriction of foetal stem arteries. Babies of such mothers are mostly small for date. [4] Histological findings like cytotrophoblastic cellular proliferation, syncytial knot formation, fibrin plaque formation etc. have

been observed in greater amount in hypertensive placentae. [5,6] Gross pathological changes are commonly seen in placentae of severe preeclampsia. The characteristic placental changes seen in preeclampsia are found to be associated with placental ischemia. In consistence with this prediction, the placenta in preeclampsia are found to be small. The gross placental changes with severe pre-eclampsia and foetal growth retardation are quite similar. [7,8]

The present study has been undertaken to assess the morphology & histology of placenta from mothers with pre-eclampsia/eclampsia and to correlate their findings with those of normal pregnancies.

As there is heightened stress and strain in the Indian women, cases of Pre-Eclampsia has drastically increased. This is one among the deadly triad in pregnancies resulting in maternal and fetal morbidities and mortalities. Placental examination will help to identify the aetiologies and pathological processes which result in adverse outcome and improving the management in subsequent pregnancies. This will also help in improving the neonatal –perinatal health care, by assessment of factors contributing to poor pregnancy outcome .It will also help in diagnosis, prediction also for the treatment of Pre-Eclampsia in future .Knowing the microscopic and the macroscopic structure of placenta can help in the effective management, to develop new strategies to prevent pregnancy complications .It will also improve the maternal health and the fetal outcome in the subsequent pregnancies.

Materials and methods:

Patients/Placentae: This is a comparative study done from January 2022 to May 2024.

A total of 100 placentae were collected, of these, 50 belonged to women diagnosed as Pre-Eclampsia (cases), and 50 placentae were taken from those who carried normal pregnancy (controls). The study was conducted in the department of obstetrics and gynaecology, NRI medical college, Sangivalasa with collaboration with Department of pathology.

Inclusion criteria: Placenta from the women having pre- eclampsia i.e. BP more than 140/90 were taken.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with other systemic disorders complicating pregnancy like diabetes mellitus, asthma, and drug dependence were exclude from the present study.

The placentas from both vaginal and cesarean deliveries were included. Immediately after the delivery, weight (wt) of the baby was taken and APGAR at 0, 1min and 5min was noted. Once the placenta was delivered, it was washed under running tap water. Umbilical cord was cut at its placental site

of insertion and placental weight was measured in grams. Gross examination of placenta was done for the presence of infarction, calcification, retroplacental hematoma and insertion of the umbilical cord. These findings were confirmed by the pathologist once the placenta was delivered to pathology department. Placenta was preserved in 10% formalin solution and then transported to Department of Pathology. Samples for histopathological sections were taken from the site of insertion of umbilical cord, centre of the placenta, any fibrotic, calcified and infarcted area on the placenta.

Tissue Processing: Once the samples were collected, the tissues taken were processed using ascending grades of ethyl alcohol, xylene, and paraffin wax in an automated tissue processor. The tissues were embedded in paraffin wax and cut at four micron intervals using a rotary microtome. They were stained with hematoxylin-eosin staining. Slides were studied under the compound microscope for study of Placental villi, size of villi, syncytial knot formation, ,fibrinoid necrosis, Stromal pathology, stromal fibrosis, calcification, and intervillous hemorrhage.

The fetal birth weight was measured using digital foetal weighing machine, APGAR score and condition at delivery , NICU referral were also noted.

The results were analysed using spss 17 software.

Results:

In the present study we have noted that Pre-Eclampsia is more frequent in the mothers of age group 21-25 followed by 26-30 [table 1].

The mean birth weight, mean placental weight was found to be lower in Pre-Eclampsia cases when compared to the normal cases. [table 2] p value was found to be less than 0.001 which is statistically significant.

The gross abnormalities noted in Pre-Eclampsia placenta are the presence of infarction (52%), calcifications (22%) [table 3] and small sized placenta [image 1C], and retroplacental haematomas (54%) [image 1B] when compared to placenta in the normal cases.

The microscopic features noticed in Pre-Eclampsia placenta [table 3] are increased syncytial knots (54%) [image 2B], fibrinoid necrosis (44%) [image 2C], stromal fibrosis (52%) [image 2D], and calcifications (28%) [image 2E]. The microscopy of normal placenta has been shown in [image 2A].

We have observed that there in a decrease in the foetal birth weight in the babies born to Pre-Eclampsia mothers and also there is a decrease in the APGAR score in these babies suggesting hypoxia (p value less than 0.001).

3 out of 50 babies born to Pre-Eclampsia were admitted in NICU i.e. 6% of the total cases.

Table 1: Maternal age group and gestational age wise distribution of the study subjects.

Age group	Control (n=50)		PE (n=50)		Total (n=100)		P value
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	
20 and below	13	26	2	4	15	15	0.01
21-25	25	50	36	72	61	61	
26-30	10	20	11	22	21	21	
31-35	2	4	1	2	3	3	
Total	50	100	50	100	100	100	
Gestational age (weeks)	Control (n=50)		PE (n=50)		Total (n=100)		P value
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	
less than 37	12	48	18	12	30	30	0.001
37	24	24	12	36	30	30	
38	9	18	14	28	23	23	
39-40	5	10	6	24	17	17	
Total	50	100	50	100	100	100	

Table 2: Showing comparison between mean birth weight and placental weight

	CA/CO	N	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	P value
Foetal Birth Weight	Cases	50	1946.32	498.108	0.001
	Controls	50	2854.04	381.794	
Placental weight	Cases	50	420.04	41.557	<0.001
	Controls	50	504.00	5.721	

Table 3: Showing comparison between the macroscopic and microscopic findings, apgar scoring , nicu admission in pre-eclampsia cases and normotensive controls

Macroscopic Feature	Control (n=50) Number present	%	PE (n=50) Number present	%	P value
Infarction (gross)	1	2	20	40	<0.001
Calcification (gross)	11	22	26	52	0.002
Retroplacental Clots	2	4	11	22	0.007
Insertion of umbilical cord	Central-45 Marginal-5	90% 10%	Central- 48 Marginal-2	96% 4%	0.461
Microscopic feature	Number present Control(n=50)	%	Number present PE(n=50)	%	P value
Syncytial knots	nil	-	27	54	<0.001
Fibrinoid necrosis	nil	-	22	44	<0.001
Stromal fibrosis	nil	-	26	52	<0.001
calcifications	11	22	18	36	0.123
Infarction	1	2	14	28	<0.001
Apgar score after 5 minutes	Number present Control(n=50)	%	Number present Cases PE(n=50)	%	P value
6	Nil	-	3	6%	<0.001
8	Nil	-	13	26%	
10	50	100%	34	68%	
NICU admission	Control(n=50)		Cases PE(n=50)		P value
Required	nil	-	3	6%	0.079

Image 1: Showing gross abnormalities in placenta of pre -eclampsia cases

Image 2: Showing histological features in normal placenta and placenta of pre-eclampsia cases

Discussion

The most common and major histopathological changes those noted in mothers with PRE-Eclampsia are cytotrophoblast cell proliferation, syncytial knots, deficiency of vasculo syncytial membrane, thickening of basement membrane, calcification, infarction, peri villus fibrin deposition and fibrinoid necrosis. This might be due to decreased utero placental blood flow. Chronic placental ischemia may be the reason leading to villus trophoblastic cell proliferation. However, this cell secretes the basement membrane substrate that

increasing the thickness of basement membrane. Increased syncytial knotting may be due to reduced fetal perfusion. The maternal and fetal circulation is represented by vasculo syncytial membrane. So, vasculo syncytial membrane deficiency attributes abnormalities in differentiation and maturation. The decreased perfusion and ischemia leads to fibrinoid necrosis. Thus, stating that, induced hypertensive pregnancy has greater detrimental effect on the fetus due to reduced maternal utero placental blood flow and placental ischemia that is secondary. Hence, it is very important to perform the morphological examination of placenta to understand the etiology

for adverse outcome enabling to take the preventive measures and reduces risk of reoccurrence in subsequent pregnancies particularly in pre-eclampsia and also in eclampsia cases (Palaskar et al, 2001; Johnson et al, 2007) [9]

In the present study, the commonest age range of the mothers in preeclampsia was 21-25 years and the age range of 26-30 years was the next common group. This is supported by another study reporting similar results in hypertensive pregnant women. [10] On the other hand, a study carried out in Ghana showed that pre-eclampsia occurred significantly more in women above 35 years and below 20 years of age. [11] In the present study there was a trend towards higher rates of pre-term delivery i.e, < 37 weeks, and low birth weight i.e, less than 2.5 kg compared to the normal pregnancy group. This is similar to other reports. [12,13] Patients of Pre-Eclampsia can be associated with positive family history. [14] Similar findings were found in another study [15]

Increased syncytial knots formed by an imbalance between the productions and shedding of villous syncytiotrophoblast were also observed in the present study and were seen statistically significant in number in the diseased placentae. It has been suggested that syncytial knots increase with increasing gestational age and may be used to evaluate villous maturity. [15,16]

The number of syncytial knots, calcifications, stromal fibrosis and fibrinoid necrosis was higher in Pre-Eclampsia group compared to control group in this study. Similar results have been observed by Gore et al [17] Saeed et al, [18] Sharma et al, [19] Pasricha et al, [20] Dhabhai et al [21] and Nafees et al. [22] They found higher number of syncytial knots in preeclamptic placenta as compared to control placenta. Khalid et al, [23] Narasimha et al [24] and Tomas et al [25] have also reported the similar findings.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the present study that there was statistically significant difference between mean birth weight of the babies and mean placental weight in control group and Pre-Eclampsia group. It also revealed striking villous lesions like increased syncytial knots, villous stromal fibrosis and fibrinoid necrosis, calcifications in placenta from preeclampsia cases as compared to placenta from normal term pregnancy. Thus, it can be concluded that preeclampsia has adverse effect on morphology of placenta and consequently affects the foetal outcome.

Hence the knowledge about the histopathological changes would be important to the gynaecologists in treating the subsequent pregnancies.

Limitations of the study: The limitations of the study are the small sample size due to which the results cannot be generalised to the whole population.

Ethical Clearance: taken from the institute ethics approval committee.

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